

GREEN MANAGEMENT- A DECIDING FACTOR FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Sattarova Dilfuza Dilshodbekovna

Mamun Universiteti “Iqtisodiyot” kafedrası dotsent v.b., PhD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18054023>

***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish maqsadlariga erishishda yashil menejmentning o'рни va roli yoritilgan. Shuningdek, asosiy e'tibor yashil va barqarorlikni boshqarish konsepsiyasi va ehtiyojini tahlil qilishga qaratildi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** barqaror rivojlanish, yashil iqtisodiyot, globallashuv, ekologik muammolar, eko-yorliqlar.*

***Аннотация.** В статье рассматриваются роль и место «зелёного» менеджмента в достижении целей устойчивого экономического развития. Основное внимание уделяется анализу концепции и необходимости «зелёного» и «устойчивого» менеджмента.*

***Ключевые слова:** устойчивое развитие, «зелёная» экономика, глобализация, экологические проблемы, экомаркировка.*

***Abstract.** The article discusses the role and place of green management in achieving the goals of sustainable economic development. The main attention is also paid to the analysis of the concept and need for green and sustainable management.*

***Keywords:** sustainable development, green economy, globalization, environmental problems, eco-labels.*

In the current globalized world, businesses face growing challenges in retaining customers while also protecting the natural environment, which has become a major priority. As people become more aware of environmental issues and the need to conserve natural resources, companies are adjusting their operations to be more environmentally responsible and to work toward sustainability, which will be essential for future business success. Green management refers to applying management practices that focus on environmental concerns. Given the importance of environmental protection, green and sustainable management is expected to play a role at every level and in every department of modern organizations, especially in an age of globalization and rapid technological development. Although many different terms are used, such as Corporate Social Responsibility, Corporate Responsibility, Responsible Entrepreneurship, and Corporate Citizenship, CSR or corporate sustainability essentially refers to the balanced integration of social and environmental considerations in business strategy and operations. It is about maintaining economic success and achieving commercial advantage by building reputation and gaining the trust of people that work with or live around the company. In other words, it means satisfying customers' demands, whilst also managing the expectations of other people, such as employees, suppliers and the surrounding community. In the present scenario of globalization and innovative technical advancements, we all are missing one thing-very important day by day, and that is greenery. And second thing is sustainability.

Green management means a process of managing business processes based on their environmental benefits. Sustainability Management means adopting business strategies and activities that meet the needs of the enterprise and its stakeholders today while protecting,

sustaining and enhancing the human and natural resources that will be needed in the future. Green and sustainable management presents unique challenges, not the least of which is the lack of standards determining what is means to be a green and sustainable product or a green company. Along with rise of green consumers, the rise of eco labelling, green advertising and importance of environmental reporting clearly observed. According to Brown and Ratledge, "Green Management is defined as an establishment that produces green output"[1].

Figure 1

Nature of green management

Nature-Based Knowledge and Technology	It involves emulating one's own self in terms of growing their own food, harnessing their energy, constructing things, conducting business, healing themselves, processing information and designing their communities.
Products of Service to Products of Consumption	Products of Service are durable goods unlike products of consumption which have shorter life span. Products of Service are made of technical materials unlike products of Consumption which are made only of biodegradable materials.
Solar, Wind, Geothermal and Ocean Energy	These are used extensively without any negative effect on the earth.
Local-Based Organizations and Economies	This characteristic includes durable, beautify and health communities with locally owned and operated business and locally managed non-profit organizations, along with regional corporations and shareholders working together in partnerships and other collaborations.
Value Production	The triple value production establishes three simultaneous requirements of sustainable business activities as financial benefits for the company, natural world betterment, social advantages for the employees and members of the local community
Continuous Improvement Process	The continuous process of monitoring, analysing, redesigning and implementing is used to intensify value production as conditions change and new opportunities emerge.

Source: <https://www.bimkadapa.in/materials/GBM-5-UNITS-PDF.pdf>

Concept of Green Management describes the construction of business. In other words, business management styles focuses on the utilization of competent and talented employees to produce profits on behalf of the business. Green Business Management is not a concept describing new business management style. It describes the construction of businesses. A Business functioning in a capacity where no negative impact is made on the local or global environment or the community or the economy. A Business that serves to meet the triple bottom line often, businesses have progressive environmental and human rights policies. A Green Business will also engage in forward thinking policies affecting human rights. These businesses adopt principles, policies and practices that improve the quality of life for their customers, employees and environment.

Figure 2

Types of Green Management

Source: <https://www.bimkadapa.in/materials/GBM-5-UNITS-PDF.pdf>

The rise of ecolabelling, green advertising and environment reporting are clearly observed, during the conduct of study, which radically reduces material, energy, waste, saves environment and finally helps sustain life. Green and Sustainability Management is growing greatly as increasing number of consumers and customers are willing to back their environmental consciousness with their rupees. Green and Sustainability Management also effects company’s public image. Green washing (presenting a product or service as green when it’s not) should not be practiced as it leads to loss of customers and decrease in profit levels.

1.Green and Sustainability Management is an effective tool to satisfy the needs and wants of environment friendly consumers and customers leading to customer and consumer loyalty.

2. n the globalized hi-tech business world. Green and Sustainability Management significantly affects a company’s public image.

3.Standardized Green and Sustainability Management increases the profits and market share of an organization.

4.Green and Sustainability Management acts as an effective tool to minimize the risk of environment friendly customer and consumer loss in this tough competitive business world.

5.Green and Sustainability Management helps in sustaining business as well as life by saving natural environment.

REFERENCES

1. DT Brown, EC Ratledge [Energy, the environment and delaware jobs: Defining and describing green business](#) - University of Delaware, 116. Retrieved on May 2nd ..., 2011
2. United Nations, Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, 2015. Available: <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
3. Hardeep Singh & Bikram Pal Singh.Green and sustainable management – A deciding factor for tomorrow’s business. Volume No.- 2 (2011), Issue No. (April), International Journal Of Research in Commerce & Management.
4. Wales, T. (2013). ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY: WHAT IS IT, AND WHY DOES IT MATTER?. Review of Enterprise and Management Studies, 1 (1), 38–49.